

AI-Based education interventions, STEM literacy and career interest among undergraduate science education students in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated AI-Based education interventions, STEM literacy and career interest among undergraduate science education students in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. A descriptive survey research design was used for the study. The population of the study consisted of all the science education students' in public universities in Akwa Ibom State. 140 students in 300 level were selected by simple random sampling from the two public universities in the area of study. Researchers made instrument titled: AI-Based Education Intervention, STEM Literacy and Career Interest Questionnaire (AEISLCIQ) was used for data collection. The reliability of the instrument was 0.72 and 0.93 determined using Cronbach Alpha statistics. Data obtained was analysed with the use of Pearson moment correlation statistics. Findings showed a non-significant positive relationship between STEM literacy and AI-based education intervention among undergraduate science education students. There was a significant positive relationship between career interest and AI-based education intervention among undergraduate science education students in Akwa Ibom State. In line with the findings, recommendation were offered among others that AI-based tools and resources should be incorporated into teaching practice to enhance STEM literacy among students. Policymakers should develop targeted interventions to promote career interest in STEM fields particularly students who are disengaged and uninterested.

Keywords: AI-Based interventions, STEM literacy, career interest, undergraduates and science education

Introduction

The increasing global demand for technologically proficient citizens has prompted an advancement in tertiary institution, particularly for training of undergraduate science education students. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a broad concept that involves a variety of analytical approaches, which are generally categorized into machine learning, neural networks, and deep learning (Aggarwal, 2018). Machine learning refers to the ability of computer algorithms to learn from data and make decisions without explicit programming (Popenici & Kerr, 2017). While there are many models within machine learning, the most commonly applied are Supervised algorithms which rely on labeled sample data (training data) to build predictive models; and unsupervised algorithms which work with unlabeled data to independently identify hidden patterns not previously recognized by humans (Alenezi & Faisal, 2020).

In the field of education, AI has been applied in multiple ways. For example, it supports technologies such as chatbots (Alotaibi, Ali, Alharthi, & Almehamdi, 2020), intelligent tutoring

systems, and automated grading tools (Heffernan & Heffernan, 2014). These AI-driven educational interventions create opportunities for learners, teachers, and other stakeholders to enhance the teaching and learning process (Chan & Hu, 2023). With its growing integration into classrooms globally, AI continues to reshape instructional practices and learning environments, Nigerian universities must adapt curricula to include AI-based interventions, such as intelligent tutoring systems, adaptive learning platforms, and interactive simulations in order to cultivate pedagogical competence and digital fluency (Holmes, Bialik, & Fadel, 2019; Hwang et al., 2020). Several applications of AI-based interventions useful in instruction include: Project-based learning such as google's blockly: it teaches programming concepts through block-based coding; Makey Makey: an invention kit promoting creativity and innovation. Coding and Programming tools such as scratch: it teaches programming concepts through block-based coding; CodeCombat: a coding platform using game design and AI; NetLogo: an agent-based modeling and simulation platform. Simulations and Modeling such as PhET and CK-12: which serves as a communicating simulation used in science and math. Virtual Labs such as LabXchange: virtual labs and simulations for science education; PraxiLabs: virtual labs for science experiments. Personalized Learning platform such as Kiddom: AI-powered learning platform for science education; DreamBox Learning: an AI-powered math and science learning platform; Khan Academy's AI-powered learning platform: provides personalized learning experiences. Science Content Creation; Wolfram Alpha: AI-powered calculator for science and math; Curipod: AI-powered tool for creating interactive science lessons. The National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013) mandates the infusion of information technology into all teacher training programmes. Yet, implementation remains uneven due to infrastructural, pedagogical, and policy constraints (Nja et al., 2023; Jack & Songo, 2020). A study by Eden, Matthew, Umoetuk, Akpan (2024) on artificial intelligence approval and computer anxiety of science education teachers' in Akwa Ibom State observed that challenges abound for integration of AI such as lack of provision of the needed technological devices, the cost of purchase of electronic devices, cost of installation and maintenance among others. This has great impact on the undergraduate student's ability to utilize these technologies for learning, STEM literacy, career interest and advancement in our public universities.

STEM literacy involves scientific knowledge, mathematical reasoning, engineering concepts, and technological proficiency which are very essential for preparing future educators to drive innovation in science teaching (Tanak, 2018). In Nigeria, Eze and Okafor (2022) found that undergraduates exposed to AI-enhanced simulations and virtual labs exhibited deeper conceptual understanding than those taught via traditional methods. Similarly, Jack and Songo (2020) reported that access to AI-supported digital resources significantly boosted students' abilities to analyse scientific data and apply theoretical principles in practical contexts. Despite these advancements, many Nigerian institutions face challenges such as limited AI infrastructure, inadequate faculty training, and outdated curricula. These observations tend to hamper the realization of STEM literacy goals (Oluwatimilehin, 2021). Addressing these gaps requires strategic investment in AI tools, curriculum redesign, and collaborative research on AI-based pedagogy.

Undergraduate science education students' career aspirations are also strongly influenced by technology-supported learning experiences. Nja et al. (2023) observed that project-based learning incorporating AI tools increased motivation to pursue careers in environmental science, engineering, and science education. Okoli and Osuafor (2018) further showed that students with high digital self-efficacy were more inclined toward roles in educational technology and curriculum

development. Computer anxiety of teachers as observed by Eden et al. (2024) also contributes to the utilization of AI-based tools by teachers.

Career choices, however, are also shaped by perceived job security, mentorship availability, and institutional support. Dike (2019) found that undergraduates in rural universities were less likely to pursue STEM careers due to scarce role models and digital infrastructure deficits. It is not yet clear if there is any significant influence of the utilization of AI-based educational intervention tools and undergraduates STEM literacy and career interest. Hence the need for this study is ascertain the relationship between AI-Based education interventions, STEM literacy and career interest among undergraduate science education students in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria and to offer recommendations that can foster a comprehensive training of the STEM educator.

Statement of the Problem

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is become the transformative tool in education, offering individualized involvements, adjusted evaluation, and synchronous results. Globally, AI-based interventions have shown promise in enhancing learning aftermaths in STEM disciplines. However, the integration of AI into Nigeria's educational system, especially at the undergraduate level, remains in its nascent stages, with limited empirical studies examining its effectiveness in enhancing STEM literacy and influencing career interests among students. This study seeks to investigate the potential of AI-based educational interventions in enhancing STEM literacy and stimulating career interest among undergraduate science education students in Akwa Ibom State. Such an inquiry is essential to inform policy decisions, curriculum development, and the implementation of innovative teaching methodologies that align with global best practices.

Objectives of the study

1. To examine the relationship between STEM literacy and AI-based education intervention among undergraduate science education students Akwa Ibom State.
2. To ascertain the relationship between career interest and AI-based education intervention among undergraduate science education students Akwa Ibom State

Research questions

1. What is the relationship between STEM literacy and AI-based education intervention among undergraduate science education students Akwa Ibom State?
2. What is the relationship between career interest and AI-based education intervention among undergraduate science education students Akwa Ibom State?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between STEM literacy and AI-based education intervention among undergraduate science education students Akwa Ibom State.
2. There is no significant relationship between career interest and AI-based education intervention among undergraduate science education students in Akwa Ibom State.

Methods

A descriptive survey research design was employed for the study. The population of the study consisted of all the science education students' in public universities in Akwa Ibom State. 140 undergraduate students were sampled from 300 level students in the two public universities in the area of study using simple random sampling technique. Researchers made instrument titled: AI-Based Education Intervention, STEM Literacy and Career Interest Questionnaire (AEISLCIQ) was used to collect data. The instrument was made up of three parts. Part A was the Bio-data of the participants, B consisted of ten (10) item statement used to obtain opinion of respondents on AI-Based education interventions while C consisted of ten (10) item statement used collect data on

STEM literacy of undergraduate science education students, while section D consisted of ten (10) statements designed to obtain opinion of respondents on the career interest of science education students. The instrument was developed on a four-point Likert scale with Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) with 4, 3, 2, and 1 points respectively. The validity was done by three experts in the Department of science education of Akwa Ibom State University. The instrument was given to 30 students in the study population who were not a part of the sample size and was found to be 0.72 and 0.93 using Cronbach alpha statistics. The questionnaire was given to the respondents and retrieved immediately to obtain a high return rate. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation was used to analyse the data at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between STEM literacy and AI-based education intervention among undergraduate science education students?

Table 1: Pearson product moment correlation analysis of the relationship between STEM Literacy and AI-based intervention tools (N=140)

Variable	Mean	SD	R
STEM Literacy	2.92	0.81	0.068
AI-Based Intervention	2.31	0.78	

The information in Table 1 shows that there is a low positive relationship between STEM literacy and AI-based education intervention among undergraduate science education students in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria ($r=0.068$). This means that AI-based education intervention has an impact on STEM literacy.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between career interest and AI-based education intervention among undergraduate science education students?

Table 2: Pearson product moment correlation analysis of the relationship between career interest and AI-based education intervention (N=140)

Variable	Mean	SD	R
Career Interest	2.31	0.78	1.00
AI-Based Intervention	2.31	0.78	

The information in Table 2 shows that there is a positive relationship between career interest and AI-based education intervention among undergraduate science education students in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria ($r=1.00$). This means that AI-based education intervention has an impact on career interest of science education students.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypotheses 1: There is no significant relationship between STEM literacy and AI-based education intervention among undergraduate science education students.

Table 3: Correlation analysis of the relationship between STEM literacy and AI-based education intervention (n=140)

Variable	Mean	SD	R	p-value
STEM Literacy	2.92	0.81	0.068	0.43
AI-Based intervention	2.31	0.78		

Significant at the 0.05 level of significance.

Table 3 shows that there is a non-significant positive relationship between STEM literacy and AI-based education intervention among undergraduate science education students ($r=0.068$, $p=0.43$). This means that AI-based education intervention increases with decrease in STEM literacy among undergraduate science education students in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Hence the null hypothesis is retained.

Hypotheses 2: There is no significant relationship between career interest and AI-based education intervention among undergraduate science education students.

Table 4: Correlation analysis of the relationship between career interest and AI-based education intervention (n=140)

Variable	Mean	SD	R	p-value
Career Interest	2.31	0.78	1.00	0.00
AI-Based Intervention	2.32	0.78		

Significant at the 0.05 level of significance.

Table 4 shows that there is a significant positive relationship between career interest and AI-based education intervention among undergraduate science education students ($r=1.00$, $p=0.00$). This means that AI-based education intervention decreases with increase in career literacy among undergraduate science education students in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

Discussion

Findings of the study showed that there is a non-significant positive relationship between STEM literacy and AI-based education intervention among undergraduate science education students in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. This can be due to the instrument used in measuring STEM literacy might not have been sensitive enough to capture the changes brought about by the AI-based intervention. Despite this non-significant relationship it is still possible for AI-based education to be of great benefit to STEM literacy therefore the need for further investigation. This finding is in contrast with Jack and Songo (2020) who reported that access to AI-supported digital resources significantly boosted students' abilities to analyse scientific data and apply theoretical principles in practical contexts.

The findings of the study showed that there is a significant positive relationship between career interest and AI-based education intervention among undergraduate science education student in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. It might be due to the fact that AI-based education makes learning more interactive and engaging, which may increase students' interest in their careers by making complex concepts more accessible and enjoyable. These can also be due to perception of the undergraduate science education students about current AI tools which are captivating therefore boosting students' motivation and interest in their chosen fields. This finding is in line with Nja et

al. (2023) who found that incorporating AI tools increased motivation to pursue careers in environmental science, engineering, and science education. This finding also agrees with Okoli and Osuafor (2018) who found that students were more inclined toward roles in educational technology and curriculum development due to high digital self-efficacy. The findings of this study is in contrast with Dike (2019) who found that students had low interest to pursue STEM careers as a result of scarce role models and digital infrastructure.

Conclusion

In conclusion, AI-Based education interventions, STEM literacy and career interest among undergraduate science education students in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria showed that AI-based education can enhance students' career interests by making learning more engaging, relevant, and in line with students' future career chooses.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study it was recommended that:

1. The incorporate AI-based tools and resources into teaching practice to enhance STEM literacy among students should be encouraged by teachers.
2. Policymakers should develop targeted interventions to promote career interest in STEM fields particularly students who are disengaged and uninterested.
3. Develop well-structured professional training programs that provide educators with the necessary AI competencies, bridge existing skill gaps, and promote effective integration of AI tools into teaching practices.

References

- Aggarwal, C. C. (2018). *Neural networks and deep learning*. A text book. Springer International Publishing AG, part of Springer Nature.
- Alenezi, H. S. & Faisal, M. H. (2020). Utilizing crowdsourcing and machine learning in education: Literature review. *Education and Information Technologies*, 25, 2971-2986.
- Alotaibi, R., Ali, A., Alharthi, H. & Almehamdi, R. (2020). AI chatbot for tourist recommendations: A case study in the city of Jeddah, Saudi Arabia. *International Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies*, 18-30, 10.3991/ijim.v14i19.1720
- Chan, C. K. Y., & Hu, W. (2023). Students' voices on generative AI: Perceptions, benefits, and challenges in higher education. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-023-00411-8>
- Dike, V. E. (2019). Career interest and teaching motivation among science education undergraduates in South-East Nigeria. *African Journal of Educational Research*, 23(1), 103–117.
- Eden, M. I., Mathew, V. E., Umoetuk, E. U. & Akpan, M. U. (2024a). Artificial intelligence approval and computer anxiety of science teachers in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Journal of Research Education, Humanities and Science*, 2(1), 55-63
- Eden, M. I., Udo, A. L & Mbuk, W. E. (2024b). Availability and level of usage of emerging technologies in science education in public and private Universities in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Journal of Research Education, Humanities and Science*, 2(1), 55-63
- Eze, C. I. & Okafor, L. J. (2022). Impact of virtual laboratories on pre-service science teachers' STEM literacy in Enugu State. *West African Journal of Science Education*, 9(4), 88–101.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN), (2013). *National Policy on Education*. Lagos: NERDC press.

- Holmes, W., Bialik, M. & Fadel, C. (2019). *Artificial Intelligence in Education: Promises and Implications for Teaching and Learning*. Boston: Boston Consulting Group. Means, B., Hwang, G. J., Xie, H., Wah, B. W., & Gašević, D. (2020). Vision, challenges, roles issues of Artificial Intelligence in Education. *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence*, 1, 100001.
- Jack, G. U. & Songo, P. (2020). Availability and usage of technology-based materials for science curriculum delivery: Lecturers' perspectives in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria. *Journal of Education in Developing Areas (JEDA)*, 28 (2), 167-177.
- Nja, C. O., Idiege, K. J., Uwe, U. E., Meremikwu, A.N., Ekon, E. E., Erim, C. M., Ukah, J. U., Eyo, E. O., Anari, M. I. & Cornelius-Ukpepi, B. U. (2023). Factors influencing science teachers' Artificial Intelligence (AI) utilization in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria *Smart Learning Environments*, 10, 42
- Okoli, J. N., & Osuafor, A. M. (2018). Availability, accessibility and extent of use of new Technologies for STM Curriculum Delivery. 49th Annual Conference Proceedings of STAN.
- Oluwatimilehin, T. (2021). Challenges and prospects of AI integration in Nigerian teacher education. *Nigerian Journal of Digital Learning*, 5(1), 23–38.
- Popenici, S. A., & Kerr, S. (2017). Exploring the impact of artificial intelligence on teaching and learning in higher education. *Research and Practice in Technology Enhanced Learning*, 12(1), 22.
- Tanak, A. (2018). Designing TPACK-based course for preparing student teachers to teach science with technological pedagogical content knowledge. *Kasetsart Journal of Social Sciences*, 41, 53-59.